

DIGITAL COMPETENCIES OF A MODERN TEACHER AS BASIS FOR SUCCESSFUL TEACHING PERFORMANCE

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Abstract: The current study describes the digital competencies of teaching staff necessary for working in modern education. The authors present the well-known structures of digital competencies, analyze them and identify their own set of key competencies that contribute to the improvement of a successful pedagogical performance. The study concludes that the possession of digital competencies increases the competitiveness of teachers in the educational environment, which contributes to the success of teaching activity.

Keywords: digital competencies, successful pedagogical activity, modern educational space, ICT competencies, school teacher.

In the modern educational space, the success of the teacher's teaching activity plays an important role, which is necessary to achieve the effectiveness and productivity of the work performed if the teacher has the appropriate knowledge, skills and abilities. As E.A. Levanova and T.V. Pushkareva note, the complexity of modern socio-political activity has led to a reassessment of established values and a fundamentally new approach to the professional training of teachers [2, P. 148].

The team of researchers at the Belarusian State University notes that successful pedagogical activity depends on external and internal circumstances, which include the ability to use multimedia accompaniment in lessons and other means for organizing and conducting classes [3].

The successful teaching activity of a teacher was considered in his writings by V.I. Andreev, who assessed the competitive advantages of specialists in the field of education, highlighting professional competence and the level of knowledge acquired as the main criteria for competitiveness in the pedagogical labor market [1].

Professional competence is characterized by the unity of theoretical and practical readiness to carry out pedagogical activities and implies the possession of generalized characteristics of a teacher related to his professional activity and independent of personal qualities – competencies [4, C. 17]. One of the main competencies in the modern educational field is the possession of digital technologies.

The relevance of the work is due to the need for the formation and development of information and communication skills of a modern teacher in an educational environment. The research of A.A. Vasilyeva, N.V. Gremina, T.D. Lavrinenko, V.P. Ignatieva, N.P. Tabachuk [6] and other scientists is devoted to the topic of digital competencies of teachers. In the works of modern researchers, it is noted that e-learning as a new pedagogical environment requires new skills from teachers - digital competencies.

The scientific novelty of this work is to identify the key digital competencies of modern teachers that contribute to successful teaching activities. The aim of the work is to generalize well-known approaches to the structure of digital competencies and compile a list of key ICT competencies that affect the success of teaching activities.

Let's turn to the structure of digital competencies of teachers recommended by UNESCO. The list of competencies consists of three modules:

1. The use of ICT – preparing students to use digital technologies for social development.
2. Mastering knowledge is the formation of students' abilities for the social and economic development of their country using digital technologies.
3. Knowledge production – educating students to reproduce the acquired knowledge and participate in innovative processes.

Each of these modules includes six aspects of work: understanding the role of digital competencies in education, curriculum and assessment, pedagogical practices, ICT technical and software tools, organization and management of the educational process, professional development [5].

It should be noted that the classification of digital competencies of teachers contributes to the development of ICT competencies among students in the process of acquiring new knowledge, but does not describe the means, methods and methods of successful pedagogical activity of teaching staff.

M.S. Tsvetkova and V.M. Kiryukhin note that the digital competencies of teachers are based on general digital literacy and include the general competencies of digital pedagogy:

1. The ability to use e-learning in teaching practice.
2. Using learning platforms for mobile learning.
3. Using e-books and open educational platforms to prepare for lessons.
4. The ability to work with digital materials and a learning platform.
5. The use of online courses for advanced training in their subject [8].

The researchers focus on the competencies of general digital pedagogy, without focusing on the teacher as a subject of educational activity.

Researchers N.P. Yachina and O.G.G. Fernandez identify three main digital competencies necessary for teaching:

1. The teacher must have the ability to navigate the tools for the creation and application of educational resources.
2. The teacher should be able to distinguish between the main digital educational resources and be able to apply them in the classroom at school.
3. The ability to design an educational activity using digital educational technologies [7, C. 136].

The classification by N.P. Yachina and O.G.G. Fernandez is devoted to the teacher as a subject of educational activity. It reflects the preparation for classes on open educational resources and work with students, however, there are no platforms aimed at improving the skills of teaching staff.

We were able to analyze the well-known modern structures of digital competencies of a school teacher. It should be noted that in their professional activities, teachers need to use the following concepts of digital pedagogy in their work:

- Open educational resources,
- massive open online courses,
- electronic textbooks,
- Educational platforms,
- electronic libraries,
- Cloud-based educational systems and Internet services,

- Digital video communication,
- Global media,
- automated educational organization management systems,
- electronic portfolios and personal electronic classrooms of students.

In accordance with these competencies, we have identified three key digital competencies that affect the success of teaching activities:

1. The use of ICT platforms.
2. The ability to work in an open educational space (keeping electronic diaries, class groups on social networks, conducting lessons using distance learning technologies and ICT platforms).
3. Using digital materials in preparation for training sessions (working with e-book libraries: LitRes, NEB, EBS "BiblioRossika", E-library, etc.).

The skillful use of digital competencies allows teachers to use system solutions in their professional activities in a digital environment: collections of educational materials, educational communication tools, learning process management tools, creative student portfolios and skillful electronic diaries.

The use of digital competencies also increases the competitiveness of teachers in the professional environment and focuses on the formation of the value of education and general media literacy among students when working with information on the Internet and global media.

It is worth noting that the capabilities of the digital school are aimed at transforming the educational system into a global digital civilization. It turns out that the possession of digital competencies is the basis for successful pedagogical activities aimed at improving the skills and competitiveness of teaching staff.

As noted by M.S. Tsvetkova and V.M. Kiryukhin, the Russian education system is globalizing the digital school, within which a unified federal cloud accounting system for all students is being created [7]. It should be added that secondary school teachers should have the appropriate knowledge, skills and abilities to work with this platform.

This conclusion is confirmed by the works of N.P. Tabachuk on the study of the professional standard of a teacher in the aspect of the development of his information competence [6].

Thus, we have considered various approaches to the structure of digital competencies in the work of teachers. We noted the key competencies that affect the teaching of computer literacy to schoolchildren, the preparation and conduct of lessons using multimedia tools, as well as electronic library systems. In addition, the possession of digital competencies has an impact on the ways and means of improving the skills of teachers.

In accordance with this, it can be concluded that the possession of digital competencies increases the competitiveness of teachers in the educational space, which contributes to increasing the success of teaching activities.

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